

Stellingen

behorende bij het proefschrift:

Widely resented yet neglected: latent environmental problems

The case of an invasive alien vine on Saba and Statia

- 1 “Invasive alien species” is a label and as such accrues meaning through interpretation, which for ecologists amounts to something much more worrisome than for lay people.
- 2 The research location is not exterior to a study, but affects it to the core and should be accounted for in the research design accordingly.
- 3 Every research method will produce results – the real question is whether these are meaningful.
- 4 Science’s currency is research questions; society’s currency is problems. Trying to pay off one with the other will leave you indebted to both.
- 5 Nature of the Caribbean Netherlands is a treasure that still appears to be largely lost on the European Netherlands.
- 6 To address Coralita, one should do anything but address Coralita. Promoting land use such as agriculture and gardening holds much more potential.
- 7 There is a vacuum regarding management of invasive alien species on Saba and St. Eustatius, which should be filled by distributing responsibilities, allotting budget and involving locals.
- 8 Sitting at a desk attempting to write will almost certainly result in one of three things: chocolate, housecleaning, or a YouTube-Odyssey.
- 9 A botanist and social scientist on fieldwork is like karaoke night on a Caribbean island: a bizarre bliss and unexpectedly sense-making.

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